

First record of *Codophila maculicollis* (Dallas, 1851) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) in Cyprus

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ABSTRACT: The first record of the Eremian species *Codophila maculicollis* (Dallas, 1851) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) in Cyprus is reported. The distribution of the species in the Mediterranean Region is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Codophila maculicollis*, first record, distribution, Cyprus, Mediterranean Region.

Codophila maculicollis (Dallas, 1851) far (Hoberlandt, 1984; Rider et al., 2024; (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) Aukema, 2025).

has got an Eremian distribution (Hoberlandt, 1984). In the Mediterranean Region, the species has been reported from Algeria, Egypt, Israel, Jordan, Libya, Morocco, Syria, Tunisia and Turkey, so

Herein, the first record of *C. maculicollis* in Cyprus is reported: On 30.03.2025, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was observed and photographed north of the village of Asgata,

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located in the district of Limassol in the southern part of the island. The photo was uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Ebr & Ebrova, 2025).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Codophila maculicollis* (Dallas, 1851), near Asgata, Cyprus, 30.03.2025. (Photo: Jan Ebr and Ivana Ebrova).

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